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- Poetry
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- Others

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“THINKING ABOUT THINKING”

It never ceases to amaze me how things operate in this world that we live in. Sometimes, as I'm riding my motorcycle and taking in the diversity of people around me, the beauty of my surroundings, and the beauty of life, I can't help but marvel how God created it all and managed to keep everything under control despite the millions and billions of people on earth. It's incredible alright. But there was one thing in particular that piqued my interest and stoked my curiosity and that is why do people think differently from one another. Does anyone wonder why people think? May I ask you why are you thinking? And upon reading this you are probably thinking what is thinking now and why is it important. Well just like you, I'm so much excited to learn more and ponder what is to think about thinking.

Think about thinking, it's tricky yet informative one. Everyone thinks; it's in our nature. We all have brains, and when they're working correctly, every action we perform requires thought. A large portion of our thought processes are skewed, selfish, hazy, or disorganized. However, because we are so self-assured, we mistakenly believe that we have accurately and unbiasedly ascertained how things are. Even when our psychological norms are incorrect, we have a tendency to believe in them. Thinking about thinking is a simple definition of metacognition. Metacognition can be defined as the process in which an individual may question the way in which their mind understands, interprets and stores and process the information it may receive as well as the way in which it receives it. There are two aspects of metacognition. These are, first Reflection-thinking about what we know and second, the self-regulation managing how we go about learning.

In reflecting and understanding our own thinking, we see the importance of it in our life and our own learning process, reflecting can also be a life changing, it make us realize, it taught us lesson and sometimes it challenge our thinking capability. Self-regulation. It is increasingly important that we are able to proactively evaluate and improve upon our own thinking and learning process.

In a rapidly changing world, successful individuals must be life-long learners who are metacognitive about and able to effectively evaluate their learning. Without the capacity to concentrate and persevere, students, individuals, and the like will be constantly dragged left and right by their immediate impulses within the educational system.

Diverse people have different ideas on how to accomplish their goals, create strategies to do so, gather knowledge and information, and create systems. The likelihood that we will succeed, however, increases with our level of information about the capabilities of our mind. As what Thomas A. Edison quoted “Five percent of the people think; ten percent of the people think they think; and the other eighty-five percent would

rather die than think.” Hoping that we are part of those (10) ten percent people who think they are, will, and always, be thinking about *thinking*.

